

Interview with Tristan Garcia

Translated from the French By Sarah De Sanctis

1) The words « realism » and « anti-realism » are ancient words, almost as old as the history of Western philosophy itself. Yet these are empty concepts if they are not contextualized : one has to specify the classes of objects to which these words refer. So, can you explain on what basis you use different approaches depending on the class of objects under consideration?

Realism is not primarily defined by a content, but rather by an attitude. Realism is not the recognition of reality: it is the idea that any object determines its understanding and not the other way round (i.e. that the understanding determines the object). If by "understanding" we simply mean the fact of relating to something, we can say that a realist spirit is one that believes that everything he thinks of depends on what he thinks (i.e. the object of his thought is what the thought of the object depends on): a realist and Cantorian mathematician believes that her demonstration follows the object of her demonstration, while the anti-realist mathematician thinks that the object of the demonstration is constructed by the demonstration itself (and there are a thousand ways not to be realist in philosophy of mathematics). Regarding perception, the realist believes that what he sees (the object of his seeing) determines what he sees; the anti-realist believes that his seeing determines what he

sees. They both refer to the same relation, but in opposite directions.

Therefore, realism – in theory of knowledge, but also in ethics or politics – does not essentially proceed from the real; realism is rather the attitude of the spirit which finds its strength in the recognition of a superior strength. The realist recognizes in what he sees a greater strength than his own seeing; she recognizes in what she judges a greater strength than her own judgement. The realist admits that everything he can understand proceeds from what he understands (the object of his understanding): he celebrates the superior power of the perceived over the perceiver.

Thus, there may be as many realisms as the possible objects of perception or thought: everything that we relate to can give rise to a realism, provided that what one relates to outweighs those who relate to it. There is thus, I believe, a realism of matter (Engels' Anti-Dühring), a realism of Evolution (evolutionary psychology), a realism of society (Durkheim's "social realism", according to which society is independent of the individuals who compose it and conceive of it), a realism of culture, a realism of History, a realism of the everyday and the ordinary; there is even a realism of the possible.

This could also be a definition of Speculative Realism: that is, a realist attitude applied not to the real, but to the possible. Realistically relating to the possible means believing that the possible object has greater strength than understanding and than the conception of the possible object. It therefore means

judging that the possible is not an extension of our human cognitive apparatus or of what actually exists, but that the possible accessed by thought exists independently of thought's ability to conceive of it. There are certainly as many realisms as the possible determinations of everything that is: perhaps the realism of the possible is the widest in scope.

3) Relativism has often been treated as an extreme and necessary outcome of antirealism. Is that so? And, if not, what is the difference between relativism and antirealism?

If realism is the idea that the object determines its understanding, and if anti-realism is the idea that the understanding of the object determines the object, it could be argued that both are in some way relativisms: realism makes the understander of an object relative to the object; anti-realism makes the object relative to whoever understands it as an object. Of course, we usually mean by relativism an anti-realist position, which makes the object depend on its understanding, and not vice versa.

The anti-realist relativism consists in specifying the conditions under which an object is always understood, namely, what it should be related to in order to be determined. Outside of those conditions, a relativist does not assert that the object does not exist, but that it is not what it is. A work of art out of context, a rule or moral law out of the culture that has enacted it, a historic-specific behaviour out of its time: they all exist, but

ist, but they are no longer what they are. Understood in another context, in another culture, in another era, they are a different object. The relativist antirealist is one who states that the singular being of any object depends on certain conditions of its understanding; if these conditions are changed, the object is changed at the same time. When Nelson Goodman says that an object is a work of art under the terms of its presentation and its exposition, he makes a good example of aesthetic relativism. If the being of an object depends on the conditions of its understanding, the challenge for thought becomes to discover the conditions that, when changed, change the understanding of an object to the point of altering its identity. What are the conditions that make something what it is and that, upon changing, will make the object into something else?

Following the answer I have given, it seems to me that there are different degrees of determination of relativism. When expressing the dependence of any proposition, any truth, any value vis-à-vis a cultural, historical or social position, relativism affirms the triumph of the particular over the singular and the universal: there is nothing universal, nothing is singular because everything that is thought, said or perceived is particularized by the conditions of its perception, its conception, its enunciation. This first relativism is particularist. It says that everything that makes an object particular determines it to the point that, if the conditions of its particularity change, its uniqueness will also change: it is no longer what it is.

Obviously, the very statement of this relativism is either universal or particular. In the first case, the particularity itself is particular. We could then say that this relativism is not completely false, but that it is only true for those who give it a form of truth: it embodies this strange and fascinating thought that will only begin to be true when one wants to take it for true. In the second case, the particularity is universal: even those who believe they escaped it are stuck in it. What I think depends on my social status, my education, my gender, my historical situation, my language, the grammar of my language, the configuration of my body, the part of the light spectrum I see, the part of the sound spectrum I hear, my belonging to the human race ... If I were poorer or richer, if I had not done the same studies, I were a woman and not a man, if I were not standing on two legs, if I saw what a cat sees, if I heard what a dolphin hears, all objects in the world which I relate to would be different, and everything I take to be true might become false. Obviously, particularism then appears to be a necessary exception to its own rule: even if I were radically different, it would still be true that everything I know and perceive depends on my particularities. Nothing is universal, except for the negation of the universal itself.

Once we accept this formula, it becomes necessary to consider a second kind of relativism, one with more important consequences, that no longer has to do with the particularity of the conditions of access to an object, but the universal conditions of the relation of any subject with any object. This

universal rather than particularistic relativism becomes a statement on knowledge which postulates that there is no object without a subject of this object (that is, without a conscience, without a cognitive apparatus that identifies it, recognizes it, names it and attributes qualities to it). Any object is under the condition of that which it is the object of. Since this relativism is universal, it is necessary that the subject of the relation can relate to itself as to an object among others: the object does not come first, since it is determined by the subject who understands it, but the latter may become at any time a relative object him or herself (a relativist sociologist transforms his sociology into an object of study, the moralist who says «Truth on this side of the Pyrenees, error on the other side » passes to the other side of the mountains...).

What is left ? What is left is the relation. And universal relativism always ends up turning into relational universality.

The dependence of the object on the subject is nothing but a special case of dependence of the object on another object. In this latter form of relativism, any entity in general is what it is only insofar as it is connected to another entity. In relation to a given object or class of objects, I am like this; but in relation to another object or to any other class of objects, I am like that. All changes, even my maxims on the variation of all things. The subject of universal relativism is ready to submit her relativism to relativity. What remains is the relation: in relation to itself, relativism is true; in relation to its refutation, it is wrong. Relational

relativism does not say that everything is relative, but that everything is related. It argues that there is no support for these relations outside of these relations themselves, and that what is related is an effect of the relations themselves.

When it is perfectly consequent, then I think that any relativism, step by step, leads not to the idea that everything is relative (this is simply a possible content of relativism), but that there is nothing in reality but relations, and relations of relations.

3) Relativism is particularly hard to refute in ethics. What can be the consequences of adopting a realist perspective, from this point of view?

There is an ethical promise in any relativism, without which it would not be attractive: the promise to treat equally everything I can get in relation with, and to respect the uniqueness of every object perceived or thought. Relativism, especially moral and political, promises to adapt its understanding of a phenomenon to what the phenomenon is, rather than adapting the phenomenon to the understanding we want to have of it. This is a very worthy ideal: to treat equally the other and the same, to find an equal footing to account for everything that occurs.

I think the Achilles' heel of relativism, when it is expressed in ethics, is always the confusion it ends up making between equality and equivalence. Initially, a relativist position is appealing to the democratic spirit

because it promises equal dignity to every position, every belief, every thought, every perception of an object: everything that is something is something equally. The great ontological strength of relativism is to suggest that everything which we can get in relation with (by perceiving, imagining, thinking it) is something. And no thing is more or less than another. Relativism, being a kind of realism of the relations, regards everything that enters into a relation as equally real: what is not in relation to anything is nothing.

But if we reverse the proposition, a relation is never a relation with nothing. And as it is a relation, it cannot be a relation with everything because in that way there would not be the everything that comes into relation with it. The relation thus ensures that everything that appears is neither nothing nor everything. It is something. It is something more or something less, but it is never more or less anything, it is equally something.

But by relating equal possibilities, relational relativism makes them equivalent, and therefore replaceable by one another. The relativist therefore thinks that what is equal is replaceable by anything, because anything else is worth it. What is unique thus becomes common. Equality is supposed to ensure the uniqueness of each entity. But equivalence transforms this singularity into a non singular character: nothing is more common than being singular ... In the eyes of the relativist, everything is equally singular, so nothing is. Wanting to establish the uniqueness of every possibility, the rela-